

A NOTE ON DOMINATION CONNECTIVITY OF PATHS AND CYCLES

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ABSTRACT. Let $G = (V, E)$ be a connected graph and S is a vertex set of G . If $G - S$ is disconnected and every disconnected component has domination number equals k , then minimum cardinality of the set S is called k -domination connectivity number of G and denoted as $\kappa^{\gamma(k)}(G)$. In this study we compute 2-domination connectivity of paths and cycles.

1. INTRODUCTION

Problems with VLSI design benefit greatly from the application of the dominance concept in computer science. Domination is additionally being utilized to address security issues for interconnection networks. So far in graph theory, about forty different domination parameters have been developed [1, 2]. Connectivity is a crucial instrument for evaluating the fault tolerance of networks [3]. Harary invented the unique sort of connectivity known as conditional connectivity in 1983 [4]. According to Harary's method, each unconnected component subnetwork has some unique desired qualities. Following this ground-breaking research, several novel conditional connectivity measures, including restricted connectivity, additional connectivity, component connectivity, cycle edge connectivity, structure connectivity, and regular edge connectivity, have been defined to better understand the fault tolerance capabilities of multi-processor systems. We suggest the interested reader to the following sources for more information on these conditional connection measures that is current [5, 6, 7, 8, 9, 10, 11, 12, 13, 14, 15]. We note that the relevant literature does not contain any conditional connectivity measurements based on both domination and connectedness ideas. To close this gap, we firstly define "domination connectivity" as a novel conditional connectivity invariant of graph theory.

Let $G = (V, E)$ a connected graph where V is the vertex set and E is the edge set. The degree of any vertex(atom, node) of G is the number of edges(bond, link) incident to this vertex and denoted as, deg_v for the vertex v of V . If all the degrees of the vertices of G equal r , then G is called r -regular graph. 2-regular connected graphs with n -edge and n -vertex are called cycles and denoted as C_n . If an edge deleted from the cycle C_n then the path graph P_n is acquired. Connectivity of a connected graph G , $\kappa(G)$, is the minimum number of vertices whose deletion make the graph G disconnected. And now we firstly give the definition of a novel conditional connectivity measurement in

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graph theory literature; k-domination connectivity such as: Let $G = (V, E)$ be a connected graph and S is the vertex set of G . If $G - S$ is disconnected and every component has domination number is equal to k , then minimum cardinality of the set S is called k-domination connectivity number of G and denoted as $\kappa^{\gamma(k)}(G)$. And now, we begin to compute the 2-domination connectivity for paths and cycles.

2. MAIN RESULTS

Proposition 2.1. For $n \geq 9$, $\kappa^{\gamma(2)}(P_n) = \lfloor \frac{n}{7} \rfloor$.

Proof. We know from the definition of 2-domination connectivity that every disconnected component of P_n has domination number two. Therefore, all disconnected components must be following paths P_4 , P_5 or P_6 , since they are only paths have domination number two. Each path graph can be disconnected into by using following suitable paths P_4 , P_5 or P_6 according to n . There are seven cases in this proof.

Case 1: $n \equiv 0(\text{mod}7)$. In this case we must disconnected P_n into $k + 1$ numbers of suitable P_4 , P_5 and P_6 since $n = 7 \times k$. Therefore, it is enough to delete k numbers of suitable vertices from P_n . Thus, $\kappa^{\gamma(2)}(P_n) = \lfloor \frac{n}{7} \rfloor$.

Case 2: $n \equiv 1(\text{mod}7)$. In this case we must disconnected P_n into $k + 1$ numbers of suitable P_4 , P_5 and P_6 since $n = k \times 7 + 1$. Therefore, the number of disconnected components is $k + 1$. And we need to delete at least k numbers of suitable vertices from P_n . Thus, $\kappa^{\gamma(2)}(P_n) = \lfloor \frac{n}{7} \rfloor$.

We omit the proofs of the other cases which their proofs are similar to proofs of Cases 1 and 2. \square

Proposition 2.2. For $n \geq 10$, $\kappa^{\gamma(2)}(C_n) = \lceil \frac{n}{7} \rceil$.

Proof. As in the proof of Proposition 2.1, each cycle graph can be disconnected into by using following suitable paths P_4 , P_5 or P_6 according to n . There are seven cases in this proof.

Case 1: $n \equiv 0(\text{mod}7)$. In this case we must disconnected C_n into $k + 1$ numbers of suitable P_4 , P_5 and P_6 since $n = 7 \times k$. Therefore, it is enough to delete k numbers of suitable vertices from C_n . Thus, $\kappa^{\gamma(2)}(C_n) = \lceil \frac{n}{7} \rceil$.

We omit the proofs of the other cases which their proofs are similar to proofs of Case 1. \square

3. CONCLUSION

In this letter, a novel field of study named as k-domination connectivity is emerged by combining the concepts of domination and connectivity terms which are two independent subjects of graph theory. We compute 2-domination connectivity of paths

and cycles. This study has a potential to stimulate further the following researches: Computing 2-domination connectivity in graph operations, Reckoning k-domination connectivity for paths, cycles, complete graphs, alternating group networks and graph operations for different values of k, Calculating k-domination for well-known interconnection networks. Defining and analysing other type of domination connectivity such as: total domination connectivity, restrained domination connectivity, rainbow domination connectivity, stratified domination connectivity, Roman domination connectivity etc.

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